

Atlas Lisažuovih figura
— određivanje odnosa frekvencija —

Predrag Pejović

24.09.2015, 17:47

$$f_x : f_y = 1 : 1$$

Slika 1: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 2: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

Slika 3: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 4: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 1 : 2$$

Slika 5: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 6: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

Slika 7: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 8: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 1 : 3$$

Slika 9: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 10: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

Slika 11: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 12: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 1 : 4$$

Slika 13: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 14: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

Slika 15: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 16: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 1 : 5$$

Slika 17: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5 \omega t)$

Slika 18: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5 \omega t)$

Slika 19: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5 \omega t)$

Slika 20: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5 \omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 1 : 6$$

Slika 21: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 22: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

Slika 23: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 24: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 1 : 7$$

Slika 25: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 26: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

Slika 27: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 28: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 1 : 8$$

Slika 29: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 30: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

Slika 31: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 32: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 1 : 9$$

Slika 33: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 34: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

Slika 35: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 36: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 1 : 10$$

Slika 37: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 38: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

Slika 39: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 40: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 2 : 1$$

Slika 41: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 42: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

Slika 43: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 44: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 2 : 2$$

Slika 45: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 46: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

Slika 47: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 48: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 2 : 3$$

Slika 49: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 50: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

Slika 51: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 52: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 2 : 4$$

Slika 53: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 54: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

Slika 55: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 56: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 2 : 5$$

Slika 57: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 58: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

Slika 59: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 60: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 2 : 6$$

Slika 61: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 62: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

Slika 63: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 64: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 2 : 7$$

Slika 65: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 66: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

Slika 67: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 68: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 2 : 8$$

Slika 69: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 70: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

Slika 71: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 72: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 2 : 9$$

Slika 73: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 74: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

Slika 75: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 76: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 2 : 10$$

Slika 77: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 78: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

Slika 79: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 80: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 3 : 1$$

Slika 81: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 82: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

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Slika 84: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 3 : 2$$

Slika 85: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 86: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

Slika 87: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 88: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 3 : 3$$

Slika 89: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 90: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

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Slika 92: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 3 : 4$$

Slika 93: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 94: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

Slika 95: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 96: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 3 : 5$$

Slika 97: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 98: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

Slika 99: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 100: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 3 : 6$$

Slika 101: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 102: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

Slika 103: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 104: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 3 : 7$$

Slika 105: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 106: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

Slika 107: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 108: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 3 : 8$$

Slika 109: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 110: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

Slika 111: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 112: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 3 : 9$$

Slika 113: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 114: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

Slika 115: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 116: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 3 : 10$$

Slika 117: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 118: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

Slika 119: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 120: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 4 : 1$$

Slika 121: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 122: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

Slika 123: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 124: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 4 : 2$$

Slika 125: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 126: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

Slika 127: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 128: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 4 : 3$$

Slika 129: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 130: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

Slika 131: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 132: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 4 : 4$$

Slika 133: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 134: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

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Slika 136: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 4 : 5$$

Slika 137: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 138: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

Slika 139: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 140: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 4 : 6$$

Slika 141: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 142: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

Slika 143: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 144: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 4 : 7$$

Slika 145: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 146: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

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Slika 148: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 4 : 8$$

Slika 149: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 150: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

Slika 151: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 152: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 4 : 9$$

Slika 153: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 154: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

Slika 155: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 156: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 4 : 10$$

Slika 157: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 158: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

Slika 159: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 160: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 5 : 1$$

Slika 161: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 162: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

Slika 163: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 164: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 5 : 2$$

Slika 165: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 166: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

Slika 167: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 168: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 5 : 3$$

Slika 169: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 170: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

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Slika 172: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 5 : 4$$

Slika 173: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 174: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

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Slika 176: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 5 : 5$$

Slika 177: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 178: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

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Slika 180: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 5 : 6$$

Slika 181: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 182: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

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Slika 184: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 5 : 7$$

Slika 185: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 186: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

Slika 187: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 188: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 5 : 8$$

Slika 189: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 190: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

Slika 191: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 192: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 5 : 9$$

Slika 193: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 194: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

Slika 195: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 196: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 5 : 10$$

Slika 197: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 198: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

Slika 199: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 200: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 6 : 1$$

Slika 201: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 202: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

Slika 203: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 204: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 6 : 2$$

Slika 205: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 206: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

Slika 207: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 208: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 6 : 3$$

Slika 209: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 210: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

Slika 211: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 212: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 6 : 4$$

Slika 213: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 214: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

Slika 215: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 216: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 6 : 5$$

Slika 217: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 218: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

Slika 219: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 220: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 6 : 6$$

Slika 221: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 222: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

Slika 223: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 224: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 6 : 7$$

Slika 225: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 226: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

Slika 227: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 228: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 6 : 8$$

Slika 229: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 230: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

Slika 231: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 232: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 6 : 9$$

Slika 233: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 234: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

Slika 235: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 236: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 6 : 10$$

Slika 237: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 238: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

Slika 239: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 240: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 7 : 1$$

Slika 241: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 242: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

Slika 243: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 244: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 7 : 2$$

Slika 245: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 246: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

Slika 247: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 248: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 7 : 3$$

Slika 249: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 250: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

Slika 251: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 252: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 7 : 4$$

Slika 253: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 254: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

Slika 255: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 256: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 7 : 5$$

Slika 257: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 258: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

Slika 259: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 260: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 7 : 6$$

Slika 261: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 262: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

Slika 263: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 264: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 7 : 7$$

Slika 265: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 266: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

Slika 267: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 268: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 7 : 8$$

Slika 269: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 270: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

Slika 271: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 272: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 7 : 9$$

Slika 273: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 274: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

Slika 275: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 276: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 7 : 10$$

Slika 277: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 278: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

Slika 279: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 280: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 8 : 1$$

Slika 281: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 282: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

Slika 283: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 284: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 8 : 2$$

Slika 285: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 286: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

Slika 287: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 288: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 8 : 3$$

Slika 289: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 290: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

Slika 291: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 292: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 8 : 4$$

Slika 293: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 294: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

Slika 295: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 296: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 8 : 5$$

Slika 297: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 298: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

Slika 299: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 300: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 8 : 6$$

Slika 301: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 302: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

Slika 303: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 304: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 8 : 7$$

Slika 305: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 306: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

Slika 307: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 308: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 8 : 8$$

Slika 309: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 310: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

Slika 311: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 312: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 8 : 9$$

Slika 313: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 314: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

Slika 315: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 316: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 8 : 10$$

Slika 317: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 318: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

Slika 319: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 320: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 9 : 1$$

Slika 321: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 322: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

Slika 323: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 324: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 9 : 2$$

Slika 325: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 326: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

Slika 327: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 328: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 9 : 3$$

Slika 329: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 330: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

Slika 331: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 332: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 9 : 4$$

Slika 333: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 334: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

Slika 335: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 336: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 9 : 5$$

Slika 337: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 338: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

Slika 339: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 340: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 9 : 6$$

Slika 341: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 342: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

Slika 343: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 344: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 9 : 7$$

Slika 345: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 346: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

Slika 347: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 348: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 9 : 8$$

Slika 349: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 350: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

Slika 351: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 352: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 9 : 9$$

Slika 353: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 354: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

Slika 355: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 356: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 9 : 10$$

Slika 357: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 358: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

Slika 359: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 360: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 10 : 1$$

Slika 361: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 362: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

Slika 363: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(\omega t)$

Slika 364: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 10 : 2$$

Slika 365: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 366: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

Slika 367: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(2\omega t)$

Slika 368: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(2\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 10 : 3$$

Slika 369: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 370: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

Slika 371: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(3\omega t)$

Slika 372: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(3\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 10 : 4$$

Slika 373: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 374: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

Slika 375: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(4\omega t)$

Slika 376: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(4\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 10 : 5$$

Slika 377: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 378: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

Slika 379: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(5\omega t)$

Slika 380: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t), y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(5\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 10 : 6$$

Slika 381: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 382: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

Slika 383: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(6\omega t)$

Slika 384: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(6\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 10 : 7$$

Slika 385: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 386: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

Slika 387: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(7\omega t)$

Slika 388: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(7\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 10 : 8$$

Slika 389: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 390: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

Slika 391: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(8\omega t)$

Slika 392: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(8\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 10 : 9$$

Slika 393: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 394: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

Slika 395: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(9\omega t)$

Slika 396: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(9\omega t)$

$$f_x : f_y = 10 : 10$$

Slika 397: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 398: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$

Slika 399: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \cos(10\omega t)$

Slika 400: $x = 4 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$, $y = 3 \operatorname{div} \sin(10\omega t)$